

FAMILY OWNERSHIP: BRIDGING THE GAP BETWEEN CORPORATE GOVERNANCE AND FIRM'S PERFORMANCE: EVIDENCE FROM PAKISTAN

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14981704>

Received	Revised	Accepted	Published
11 January, 2025	11 February, 2025	26 February, 2025	06 March, 2025

ABSTRACT

The main objective of the present study is to test the impact of Corporate Governance (CG) attributes on Firm Performance (FP) with the moderating role of Family Ownership (FOWN). FP is measured with three distinct proxies, i.e., Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and Tobin's Q (TBQ). The sample of this study consists of 50 non-financial companies from the KSE-100 index. The data were collected from 2017 to 2022, making a total of 300 firm-year observations. For data analysis, the regression fixed effect technique is used for the three models. The results of the study revealed that one CG attribute, Board Size (BS), is positively and significantly related to FP. In addition to that, the moderating effect of FOWN is also significant in BS only. According to the results of this study, the significance of CG and family ties for FP proves to be worth the attention of policymakers, non-financial companies, regulatory bodies, and stakeholders for future aspects.

Keywords: Corporate Governance, Firm Performance, Family Ownership, and Agency Theory

INTRODUCTION

The debate on corporate governance (CG) has been ongoing among researchers and practitioners (Aksar et al., 2022; Khan & Mahmood, 2023) to align agents' concerns for transparent business operations to increase value for stakeholders of the firm (Arora & Bodhanwala, 2018). Since the past two decades in developing countries, the CG and Firm Performance (FP) relationship has been one of the most discussed topics, therefore many authors have tried to explore their relationship (Bhagat & Bolton, 2019; Ciftci et al., 2019; Danoshana & Ravivathani, 2019).

Good CG practices lead to the firms' sustainable value while unstable and poor CG is dreadful for the firms' value (Kyere & Ausloos, 2021). Many researchers in the past have emphasized the need to improve the FP by following good CG practices and structures (Kyere & Ausloos, 2021; Nizam et

al., 2022), because it directly relates to the shareholders and investors of the company for their current and future decisions. Good CG practices shape the firms' activities efficiently and effectively; therefore, CG practices influence the firm's specific characteristics, including FP.

In prior research, many authors studied the relationship between CG practices and FP with the inclusion of audit quality (Kazmi et al., 2024), country governance (Wu, 2021), corporate social responsibility (Rasheed et al., 2023), capital structure (Mansour et al., 2022), innovation (Jamal et al., 2024), directors' demographic characteristics (Aleemi & Uddin, 2020), competitive advantage (Rasheed & Ahmad, 2022), board gender diversity (Hussain et al., 2024) and family ownership (Amin et al., 2022). The findings of these studies are unanimous that CG

attributes positively impact FP (Gupta & Chauhan, 2023; Jensen, 1976; Saidat et al., 2019). There are many aspects of firm characteristics, such as demographic (Al-Dmour et al., 2018), structural, monitoring, and performance characteristics (Huafang & Jianguo, 2007; Olowokure et al., 2016; Wallace et al., 1994). However, this study focuses on a firm's performance characteristics.

Based on the agency theory, it is expected by the principal to attain a high-level return on their investments. Conflicts between managers and shareholders may arise if managers work to achieve their own goals; therefore, CG is an essential aspect for resolving such conflicts (Samaduzzaman et al., 2015). The findings of prior studies revealed that CG is not only beneficial in principal-agent conflicts but also increases the FP (Alshirah et al., 2022; Azmy et al., 2019; Bawaneh, 2020; Warrad & Khaddam, 2020). Board characteristics also have an effective association with TBQ (Harvey Pamburai et al., 2015). TBQ is an important aspect for investors to evaluate the firms' future and current performance (Christensen et al., 2010).

According to prior research, many factors affect the overall CG practices and performance of the firms including audit quality (Malik et al., 2017), country governance (Wu, 2021), corporate social responsibility (Lu et al., 2021), capital structure (Mansour et al., 2022), innovation (Khan et al., 2019), directors' demographic characteristics (Aleemi & Uddin, 2020), and family ownership (Amin et al., 2022). Thus, the literature has established the fact that CG attributes positively affect the FP (Gupta & Chauhan, 2023; Jensen, 1976; Saidat et al., 2019).

Around the world, most of the companies are owned and controlled by single shareholders (sole proprietors) or their family members, which are typically termed family firms (Burkart et al., 2003). According to Claessens et al. (2000), approximately two-thirds of the public firms were controlled by families or sole proprietors in the nine East Asian countries. In dual-class stock firms, it is found that founders and their families have major voting rights compared to the managers (DeAngelo & DeAngelo, 1985). These kinds of arrangements in firms create agency problems between the managers and shareholders. In family firms, conflict occurs mostly between controlling and minority shareholders, especially

in information asymmetry, which results in a decrease in FP (Mohammed, 2019).

In Pakistan, the family-owned businesses dominate the Pakistani business market. According to Khan et al. (2022), "87% of listed firms in Pakistan have at least 10% family ownership". These family firms substantially contribute to Pakistan's economic growth. These firms traditionally give more advantages to family shareholders (majority shareholders), and this phenomenon is generally linked with the agency problems' presence, which ascends if there is family ownership with majority shareholding, and they often ignore the minor shareholder concerns (Yousaf et al., 2019). Further, Family Ownership (FOWN) also manipulates the board's decision-making capacity and composition (Tawfik et al., 2022), which ultimately may affect the FP of the firm. Given this phenomenon, this study utilises family ownership as a moderator between CG and FP.

It is chosen because of the agency theory argument that CG attributes may affect the FP (Gupta & Chauhan, 2023; Jensen, 1976; Saidat et al., 2019). In particular, FOWN is employed because of its prevalent effect on the Pakistani CG attributes and FP. Prior studies have been conducted by testing the moderating effect of family ownership and control on the relationship between female board diversity, BOD effectiveness, board independence, board size, and firm performance (Amin et al., 2022; Bazhair & Sulimany, 2023; Guizani, 2013; Kouki & Guizani, 2015; Makhoulouf et al., 2018). There is rarely a study conducted to test the moderating effect of FOWN on the relationship between CG and FP. Due to this, the current study will fill this gap by investigating the impact of CG's four distinct attributes, namely BS, BI, COWN, and BOWN on FP proxied by TBQ, ROA, and ROE, with the moderating role of FOWN. So, the main objective of the study is to investigate the impact of CG on FP with the moderating role of FOWN in the context of Pakistani firms listed in PSX.

This paper contributes to the literature strand by taking the moderating role of FOWN between CG-FP. FP is measured by ROA, ROE, and TBQ, while CG is measured with different attributes. This study is helpful for potential investors and shareholders of FOWN businesses. To protect the minority shareholding rights in family-dominant firms, the policymakers and practitioners may

benefit from this study for the restructuring or redesigning of the code of CG (Yousaf et al., 2019). The firms practising high standards of governance reflect a positive image to the potential and current investors of the firm, which possibly would reduce the funding costs (Arora & Bodhanwala, 2018).

1. Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

2.1 Underpinning Theory

The link between agents and principals is explained by the well-recognized agency theory. Separate ownership may result in conflicts of interest since shareholders and managers may have conflicting goals and agents may not act in the principal's best interests (Jensen, 1976; Judith et al., 2013). This theory provides theoretical evidence for this study along with the corporate governance attributes. This study examines the four indicators of CG to address the agency issue, which are named board size (BS), board independence (BI), concentrated ownership (COWN), and board ownership (BOWN). These indicators are taken because they may have an impact on the FP.

2.2 Corporate Governance and Firm Performance

According to the agency theory, FP depends on the principals' interest alignment with the agents' interest in the firm (Bussin et al., 2023), otherwise it will result in higher agency costs (Amin et al., 2022). Lower agency cost does not guarantee accurate alignment, but it is an attempt to keep this alignment between the principal and the agents' interests (Tang, 2022). However, the CG and FP relationship has been discussed thoroughly in the previous literature (Guney et al., 2020; Khatib et al., 2020). The agency literature suggests that monitoring and advisory governance roles may improve firm performance by controlling and directing management activities, leading to reduced agency costs (Jensen, 1976). Khatib et al. (2020) highlighted the crucial role of corporate governance in policy-setting, where directors influence a company's performance through their actions.

CG is a well-known management system that focuses on increasing the shareholders' wealth and fulfilling the concerns of the stakeholders like creditors, suppliers, and the community (Utama

& Utama, 2005). However, some of the authors have refuted these arguments and showed that there is no significant relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and firms' financial performance (Balasubramanian et al., 2008; Bebchuk & Cohen, 2005).

2.3 Board Size and Firm Performance

Existing literature explains that board size has an impact on FP (Ahulu & MacCarthy, 2019; Khatib & Nour, 2021; Ofoeda, 2017; Puni & Anlesinya, 2020). Whereas Asante-Darko et al. (2018) found no significant relationship between BS and FP. Merendino and Melville (2019) showed that lower-level BS has a positive effect on FP. Lipton and Lorsch (1992) suggest an optimal BS of eight or nine directors, while Jensen (1993) suggests a BS of around seven or eight. Thus, based on the above suggestions, it can be assumed that if the firm's BS is high or more than seven, it will have a positive effect on FP. Thus, it is hypothesized that:

H_{1a}: Board Size has a positive impact on firm performance.

2.4 Board Independence and Firm Performance

According to Fama and Jensen (1983), independent directors' significance offers valuable expertise and potentially significant connections. The BI is a crucial component of the internal CG structure, expected to significantly influence the FP and value of the firm (Guluma, 2021). BI is proxied by the proportion of the number of independent members on the board and the total number of board members (Handriani & Robiyanto, 2019). The proportion of independent directors significantly impacts FP, with smaller BS indicating stronger performance (Kao et al., 2018). Pucheta-Martínez and Gallego-Álvarez (2020) and Shan (2019) indicated an inverse effect of BI and FP. Thus, it can be assumed if a firm's independent BS is high, it will have a positive effect on FP. Hence, the hypothesis is formulated as follows:

H_{1b}: Board Independence has a positive impact on firm performance.

2.5 Concentrated Ownership and Firm Performance

COWN refers to the shares held by the largest shareholders of a firm (Brogard et al., 2017). Firms with COWN tend to outperform those with dispersed ownership (Singal & Singal, 2011). The

study reveals that ownership structure, including COWN, positively impacts firm value (Kao et al., 2018). Puni and Anlesinya (2020) examined the impact of CG mechanisms on FP. The shareholder concentration or ownership structure generally positively influenced FP. COWN had positive results with FP (Agyemang & Castellini, 2015; Bokpin, 2008). Therefore, from the above literature discussion we have hypothesized that:

H_{1c}: Concentrated ownership has a positive impact on firm performance.

2.6 Board Ownership and Firm Performance

Board members with appropriate stock ownership may be motivated to effectively monitor and oversee crucial corporate decisions, making BOWN a valuable proxy for overall good governance (Bhagat & Bolton, 2019). Haniffa and Hudaib (2006) argued that various governance mechanisms, including BOWN, facilitate managing agency conflicts and reduce costs. The alignment of interests between board members and owners can potentially reduce agency conflicts (Bussin et al., 2023). Higher BOWN can aggravate agency conflicts by encouraging controlling shareholders to exploit other shareholders' wealth, potentially leading to entrenchment (Morck et al., 1988; Shleifer & Vishny, 1997).

Prior studies explored the relationship between FP and BOWN, as calculated by the percentage of shares owned by all board members (Berke-Berga et al., 2017; Bhagat & Bolton, 2013; Krivogorsky, 2006; Tleubayev et al., 2020). BOWN has a significantly positive impact on FP (Guest, 2009). Hence, from the above-described studies, it is hypothesized that:

H_{1d}: Board ownership has a positive impact on firm performance.

2.7 Family Ownership as a Moderator

According to Tariq and Naveed (2016), BOWN can be one of these; familial, governmental, or institutional. Family Ownership (FOWN) is the most common form of COWN in both large and small firms (Gillan, 2006; Steier, 2009). In familial ownership, members share a common vision, institutional investors lead, and it refers to "the ratio of shares held by family members over the firm's shares issued" (Anderson & Reeb, 2003; Villalonga & Amit, 2006). In most cases, families own entire businesses known as family-owned

businesses. Typically, family-owned businesses involve an ownership separation among family members and their immediate families, who collectively hold the shares that form the business (Paniagua et al., 2018).

Recent research indicates that BS has a significantly positive impact on a company's financial performance, regardless of family or non-family ownership. At the same time, no one has emphasized the impact of FOWN on the BS and FP relationship. In the context of Pakistan, having a related and optimal size board can have a different level of impact on the company's performance. Therefore, by filling this gap, it is hypothesized that:

H_{2a}: FOWN moderates the relationship between BS and FP.

BI has a positive impact on firms' performance despite family or non-familial controls (Johl et al., 2016). BI and FP have a strong relationship according to the existing literature, but no one has discussed the FOWN effect on the BI and FP relationship. The board having independent and related directors can change the whole dynamics of control and direction. Consequently, by filling this gap in the study, it is hypothesized that:

H_{2b}: FOWN moderates the relationship between BI and FP.

Ciftci et al. (2019) found that firms with COWN and FOWN mostly perform better because these firms tend to tolerate more risk of poor performance. Singal and Singal (2011) found no significant performance differences between family-controlled firms and foreign-controlled firms or the state, indicating COWN as the key determinant of FP. Family-concentrated ownership is the most prevalent form of organizational governance globally (Claessens et al., 2000). Family-owned firms do not provide unique advantages for better financial performance compared to firms with COWN (Singal & Singal, 2011).

According to the agency theory, the FOWN of firms reduces the agency costs. Therefore, a higher amount of COWN can increase opportunities for family owners that will decrease the performance of firms. In this case, the FOWN and FP relationship cannot always be linear (Anderson & Reeb, 2003; Pindado et al., 2011). To study this phenomenon, we have hypothesized the following:

H_{2c}: FOWN moderates the relationship between COWN and FP.

BOWN impacts the FP due to changes in decision-making and different characteristics of the board. Because of these changing factors, family connections can change the ways of the boards to counter a specific situation. By considering this assumption, we hypothesize that: H_{2d} : FOWN moderates the relationship between BOWN and FP.

3. Methodology

3.2. Study Variables

Table 1: Measurement

Variables	Measure	Source
FP - Dependent Variable		
TBQ	The market value of the firm divided by the total assets	(Wolfe & Sauaia, 2003)
ROE	Profit before tax / total shareholders' equity	(Rasheed et al., 2018)
ROA	Profit before tax / total assets	(Allam, 2022)
CG - Independent Variable		
BS	The total number of members on the board	(Said et al., 2009)
BI	The proportion of independent directors on the board	(Cucari et al., 2018)
BOWN	Fraction of shares held by directors on the board	(Desoky & Mousa, 2012)
COWN	The fraction of shares held by the five biggest shareholders	(Farooq et al., 2022)
Moderating Variable		
FOWN	Measured as a dummy variable taken as '1' if the firm is family owned, otherwise '0'	(Abdullah & Ismail, 2016)
Control Variables		
SIZE	Natural log of total assets	(Dias et al., 2019)
LEV	Total debts / Total assets	(Khan et al., 2012)

3.3. Empirical Models

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BS_{it} + \beta_2 BI_{it} + \beta_3 BOWN_{it} + \beta_4 COWN_{it} + \beta_5 FOWN_{it} + \beta_6 BS_{it} * FOWN_{it} + \beta_7 BI_{it} * FOWN_{it} + \beta_8 BOWN_{it} * FOWN_{it} + \beta_9 COWN_{it} * FOWN_{it} + \beta_{10} SIZE_{it} + \beta_{11} LEV_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

$$ROE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BS_{it} + \beta_2 BI_{it} + \beta_3 BOWN_{it} + \beta_4 COWN_{it} + \beta_5 FOWN_{it} + \beta_6 BS_{it} * FOWN_{it} + \beta_7 BI_{it} * FOWN_{it} + \beta_8 BOWN_{it} * FOWN_{it} + \beta_9 COWN_{it} * FOWN_{it} + \beta_{10} SIZE_{it} + \beta_{11} LEV_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

$$TBQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BS_{it} + \beta_2 BI_{it} + \beta_3 BOWN_{it} + \beta_4 COWN_{it} + \beta_5 FOWN_{it} + \beta_6 BS_{it} * FOWN_{it} + \beta_7 BI_{it} * FOWN_{it} + \beta_8 BOWN_{it} * FOWN_{it} + \beta_9 COWN_{it} * FOWN_{it} + \beta_{10} SIZE_{it} + \beta_{11} LEV_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Summary statistics describe information regarding the characteristics of data. The data includes 50 entities and 6 time periods, making a total of 300 firm-year observations.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics
 Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
ROA	300	9.266	10.198	-18.722	57.966
ROE	300	26.418	41.139	-57.119	269.382
TBQ	300	0.015	0.024	0.0001	0.183
FOWN	300	0.720	0.450	0	1
BS	300	8.510	2.047	6	18
BI	300	25.198	11.336	5.882	57.143
BOWN	300	0.103	0.179	0	0.906
COWN	300	0.574	0.242	0.0003	0.999
SIZE	300	24.438	1.303	20.545	27.869
LEV	300	1.178	2.134	0.149	18.998

Table 2 presents the description of the study variables through their mean, standard deviation, maximum, and minimum values. ROA's minimum and maximum value is -18.722% and 57.966% respectively. ROE's minimum and maximum value is -57.119% and 269.382% respectively. Tobin's Q has a minimum and maximum value that lies between 0 and 1. Mean and standard deviation values of ROA, ROE, BS, BI, BOWN, COWN, and FOWN indicate that

the data is not deviated much from the mean. The value of SIZE lies between 22 and 27. LEV minimum and maximum value lies between 0 and 18. These values show that the data is normal and has no outliers present.

4.2 Correlation Matrix

The correlation matrix explains the mutual relation of variables with each other. Table 3 shows the pairwise correlation of the study variables. ROA and ROE are strongly and

positively correlated by 58.3%. In addition to that, ROA and TBQ are also very strongly and positively correlated by 70%. Then, ROE and TBQ are also strongly and positively correlated by

55.7%. Lastly, ROE and LEV are also very strongly and positively correlated by 62.3%.

Table 3: Pairwise Correlation Matrix

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
(1) ROA	1.000									
(2) ROE	0.583***	1.000								
(3) TBQ	0.700***	0.557***	1.000							
(4) FOWN	-0.294***	-0.398***	-0.318***	1.000						
(5) BS	0.099*	0.176***	0.094*	-0.164***	1.000					
(6) BI	-0.007	0.059	-0.125**	-0.150***	-0.104*	1.000				
(7) BOWN	-0.070	-0.094*	-0.130**	0.188***	0.050	-0.159***	1.000			
(8) COWN	0.151***	0.191***	0.263***	-0.260***	-0.137**	-0.113*	-0.408***	1.000		
(9) SIZE	-0.168***	-0.046	-0.229***	-0.114**	0.248**	0.236***	-0.341***	0.143*	1.000	
(10) LEV	0.027	0.623***	0.173***	-0.159***	0.137**	0.087	-0.069	0.140*	0.080	1.000

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

5. Panel Data Analysis

Fixed Effects method and Random effect methods are two prominent static panel approaches that are used in the literature (Arefin, 2018; Goswami & Panthamit, 2020; Saidi et al., 2013; Shah et al., 2016; Siddica & Angkur, 2017). The Hausman (1978) test is applied to select between Fixed

Effect and Random Effect approaches. In our study, the Hausman test values were significant ($\text{Prob} > \chi^2 = 0.0000$) for all three models indicating to choose fixed effect. Table 4 below presents the combined fixed effect results of all three models.

Table 4: Fixed Effect (Model 1, 2, & 3)

VARIABLES	(1) ROA	(2) ROE	(3) TBQ
BS	0.740 (0.949)	6.491** (2.590)	-0.0105*** (0.00172)
BI	0.0302 (0.0887)	-0.0973 (0.242)	3.87e-05 (0.000161)
BOWN	-79.61 (72.57)	182.9 (198.1)	-0.159 (0.132)
COWN	-10.11 (20.11)	86.70 (54.88)	-0.00482 (0.0365)
BS*FOWN	-0.103 (1.099)	-5.680* (3.000)	0.0113*** (0.00200)
BI*FOWN	-0.115 (0.0981)	-0.0632 (0.268)	-0.000142 (0.000178)
BOWN*FOWN	81.39 (72.66)	-177.8 (198.3)	0.156 (0.132)
COWN*FOWN	-8.227 (21.62)	-89.20 (59.02)	-0.000594 (0.0393)
SIZE	2.231* (1.161)	4.640 (3.170)	-0.0101*** (0.00211)
LEV	-1.963*** (0.505)	-7.333*** (1.379)	8.01e-05 (0.000918)
Constant	-37.50 (28.37)	-114.5 (77.42)	0.288*** (0.0515)

Observations	300	300	300
R-squared	0.109	0.151	0.296
Number of ID	50	50	50

Standard errors in parentheses

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

In Table 4, the value of R^2 for model 1 is 0.109 which means there is only a 10.9% variation in the ROA explained by board characteristics (i.e., size, independence, and ownership) and the remaining 89.1% is due to other factors (error term). In addition to that, the value of chi-square for model 1 is also significant ($p < 0.01$), indicating that the model is a good fit. Results reported in Table 4 for model 1 show that BS, BI, and SIZE are positively associated with ROA but only SIZE is significant at a 10% level ($\beta = 2.231$; $p < 0.1$). That means profitability will be improved by increasing the firm size. Larger firms also benefit from economies of scale that lead to higher ROA. On the other hand, BOWN, COWN, and LEV are negatively associated with ROA but only LEV is significant at a 1% level ($\beta = 1.963$; $p < 0.01$). Hence, Profitability will be improved by decreasing the leverage ratio. A higher leverage ratio increases the cost of capital and limits the firm's financial flexibility, which lowers the firm's profitability and ROA also. In addition to that, the results show that the FOWN doesn't moderate the relationship between the studied CG indicators and ROA.

In Table 4, the value of R^2 for model 2 is 0.151 which means there is only a 15.1% variation in the ROE due to board characteristics (i.e., size, independence, and ownership) and the remaining 84.9% is due to other factors (error term). In addition to that, the value of chi-square for model 2 is also significant ($p < 0.01$) indicating that the model is a good fit. Results reported in Table 4 for model 2 show that BS, BOWN, COWN, and SIZE are positively associated with ROA but only BS is significant at a 5% level ($\beta = 6.491$; $p < 0.05$) in line with (Merendino & Melville, 2019). Hence, profitability will be improved by increasing the number of BOD members. On the other hand, BI and LEV are negatively associated with ROE but only LEV is significant at a 1% level ($\beta = 7.333$; $p < 0.01$). Hence, Profitability will be improved by decreasing the leverage ratio. A higher leverage ratio often amplifies the financial risk that lowers the ROE of the firm. Furthermore, the results show that FOWN moderates the relationship

between BS and ROE. It means a firm with large family owners with large amounts has a significant role in the firm's performance and governance. In other words, there may be some cases where family owners with larger board sizes have different interests and orientations that do not align with firms' growth and performance, leading to lower ROE. The reason could be the agency and control issues among the BOD leading to lowering the firm's performance or ROE.

In Table 4, the value of R^2 for model 3 is 0.296 which means there is only a 29.6% variation in the TBQ due to board characteristics (i.e., size, independence, and ownership) and the remaining 70.4% is due to other factors (error term). In addition to that the value of chi-square for model 3 is also significant ($p < 0.01$) indicating that the model is a good fit. Results reported in Table 4 for model 3 show that BS, BOWN, COWN, and SIZE are negatively associated with TBQ but only BS and SIZE are significant at a 1% level ($\beta = -0.011$, $\beta = 0.010$; $p < 0.01$) in line with (Khatib & Nour, 2021). That means as the board size becomes larger it will efficiently allocate its resources and create value over time. Then, if the firm size increases, the TBQ will decrease indicate as the firm grows it fails to face challenges in maintaining management efficiently and fails to align with shareholders' interests eventually decreasing its TBQ ratio. On the other hand, BI and LEV are positively associated with TBQ, but none is significant. Additionally, the results tell us that FOWN moderates the relationship between BS and TBQ significantly. It means a firm with a larger board size and a significant number of family owners has a significant role in the firm's value and governance. The reason may be the alignment of interests between BOD and family owners with better resource allocation and strategic decisions.

BS is significantly affecting FP, so we are accepting H_{1a} . Thus, BS is a strong predictor of ROE and TBQ. In support of Balasubramanian et al. (2008), BI, BOWN, and COWN do not predict the FP significantly by rejecting H_{1b} , H_{1c} , and H_{1d} . In contrast to the previous literature, FOWN has a

significant moderating impact on BS and FP by supporting H_{2a} while BI, BOWN, COWN, and FP are not significantly moderated by FOWN by rejecting the H_{2b} , H_{2c} , and H_{2d} (Ciftci et al., 2019; Johl et al., 2016). By supporting (Singal & Singal, 2011), COWN has no significant relationship with FP in the case of family ownership. It supports the fact by Pindado et al. (2011) that FOWN and FP cannot have a linear relationship. In the present study, the control variables SIZE and LEV are significantly related to FP.

5. Conclusion

The present study intended to investigate the firms' value and profitability (FP) through CG indicators while enclosing the hypothesis and making the conceptual and empirical model for the study objectives. In this study, BS has a positive and significant relationship with ROE as supported by Merendino and Melville (2019) while BS has a negative and significant relationship with TBQ in contrast with the literature. The results of the study revealed that not all the predictors successfully predicted the FP among the 50 non-financial companies in KSE-100.

This study's findings suggest that the BS has a significant effect on the firm value and profitability of companies. With the increase in BS, the performance of the firms will be improved in the future. In addition to that, FOWN significantly moderates the relationship between BS and FP. It is indicated that larger boards may dilute the influence and control of family owners of the firms over strategic decisions which lead to possible agency issues and poor performance. On the other hand, larger boards and family owners with the same long-term objectives and interests can create value leading to better performance.

Like other research, this study also has limitations of time and resources. The first limitation is that the study is conducted among a few companies listed in KSE-100 with a limited sample size of 50 companies which is why it cannot fully explain the perspective of all the companies of Pakistan. The second limitation is that the companies were non-financial so the results cannot be implemented on financial companies. Therefore, it does not have generalizable results.

Furthermore, a similar study can be conducted by taking only financial companies listed on the Pakistan Stock Exchange. In this study, there is no

mediating role so a similar study can be conducted by testing the mediating role of FP. In addition to that, a similar study with a larger sample size can be conducted in terms of generalizability.

The present study endeavours to the significance of firm performance and governance to the policymakers, non-financial institutions, and regulatory bodies for the implementation of these results to enhance the FP for its stakeholders. The non-financial institutions will be able to further advance the firm's value, profitability, and performance through proper governance to gain the trust of investors and all its stakeholders. The policymakers will make governance policies in terms of agency problems, risk management, or improved reporting to give support to the companies. The regulatory bodies should develop regulations that accommodate accurate governance and development in view of the family-owned companies. These accumulated efforts will end up contributing to the investors' trust, business growth, economic growth, and development of the country in future.

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